

Thursday, 14 September 2023 | Comenius University Science Park, Ilkovičova 8, Bratislava

Second EMBL Information Day

Agenda

10:00-10:15 Welcome and introduction

10:15-10:45 EMBL and opportunities for scientists in Slovakia

Maria Ananchenkova, International Relations Officer, EMBL Heidelberg

Vladimir Benes, Head of Genomics Core Facility, EMBL Heidelberg

10:45-11:15 Structural Biology at EMBL: scientific services at EMBL Hamburg

Maria Garcia Alai, Head of EMBL Sample Preparation and Characterisation Facility, EMBL Hamburg

11:15-11:45 New Transversal Themes at EMBL: Microbial Ecosystems

Olivia Casanueva, Programme Manager, EMBL-EBI

11:45-12:30 **Networking lunch**

12:30-13:00 Careers at EMBL: International PhD programme

Zuzana Koskova, Predoctoral Fellow, Cuylen Group, EMBL Heidelberg

13:00-13:30 ELIXIR Europe: Opportunities for the life science data community in Slovakia

Andrew Smith, Head of External Relations, ELIXIR

13:30-13:45 Closing remarks

Introducing EMBL its missions and opportunities

14 September 2023

Maria Ananchenkova

International Relations Officer

Vladimir Benes

Head of Genomics Core Facility

EMBL's missions

Excellent research

To perform fundamental research in molecular biology

Scientific services

To offer vital services to scientists in the member states and the world

Advanced training

To train scientists, students, and visitors at all levels

Innovation and translation

To actively engage in technology transfer and industry relations

Integrating life sciences

To coordinate and integrate European life science research

EMBL, EMBO and EMBC: different organisations

Legal model: Swiss Association, est.

1964

European Molecular Biology Organisation

Mission

- Promote excellence in the life sciences in Europe and beyond, including through publishing journals and awarding fellowships
- Set up a European laboratory for the life sciences

Staff: ca. 70

Members: ca. 2000 (2023)

Intergovernmental Organization, est.

1969

EMBC

European Molecular Biology Conference

Mission

- To finance and support the majority of EMBO's activities, through the contribution of its member states

Intergovernmental Organization, est.

1974

The only laboratory-based international organization in the field of life sciences

5 missions:

- Excellent fundamental research
- Infrastructure and Services
- Advanced training
- Technology development, transfer and industry
- Integration of European life science research

Groups: over 110

Staff: ca. 2000 (2022)

EMBL member states

Member states (28)

Slovakia 2018

Austria 1974

Denmark 1974

France 1974

Germany 1974

Israel 1974

Italy 1974

Netherlands 1974

Sweden 1974

Switzerland 1974

United Kingdom 1974

Finland 1984

Greece 1984

Norway 1985

Spain 1986

Belgium 1990

Portugal 1998

Ireland 2003

Iceland 2005

Croatia 2006

Luxembourg 2007

Czech Republic 2014

Malta 2016

Hungary 2017

Montenegro 2018

Lithuania 2019

Poland 2019

Estonia 2023

Associate member state

Australia 2008

Prospect member states

Latvia

Serbia

Six sites with ca. 2000 people and >90 nationalities

EMBL-EBI

Bioinformatics

Grenoble

Structural
biology

Barcelona

Tissue biology
and disease
modelling

Hamburg

Structural
biology

Heidelberg

Life sciences

Rome
Epigenetics
and
neurobiology

EMBL and Slovakia: highlights

Collaborations with Comenius University

Memorandum of Understanding signed 2019
Hands-on 3rd gen sequencing course 2020

Over 9m data requests in 2022 alone

to EMBL-EBI databases that are critical for Slovak scientists

Building international networks

Slovak scientists in strategic EMBL meetings on structural biology infrastructure and SARS-CoV-2 sequencing

100 Slovak participants

at EMBL Courses and Conferences in 2019-2022

COMENIUS
UNIVERSITY
BRATISLAVA

The EMBL Programme: Molecules to Ecosystems

EMBL is building on its core strengths in molecular biology to gain a mechanistic understanding of life in context

EMBL has introduced new, cross-EMBL structures called Transversal Themes to establish and propel new research themes within the EMBL Programme

EMBL's nine-year turnover model allows natural development of new areas

44% turnover of group and team leaders over a 5-year period

Over 100 EMBL research groups (2021)

Opportunities to engage with EMBL in the current Programme

Take part in new
EMBL postdoc programmes

Exchange knowledge through EMBL's
expanded visitor and sabbatical
programmes

Co-development and access to new
integrated experimental
services and data resources

Collaborate with EMBL researchers to
enable key projects in
molecular study of ecosystems

Join together to share knowledge on
key issues relating to Open Science

Co-organise and participate in
workshops, courses and
conferences tailored to support the
Programme goals

Reinforce shared scientific
strengths to inform national and
international policy addressing
societal challenges

Calls open for applicants from Slovakia

EMBL's International PhD programme Call open

- **Deadline: 9 October 2023**
- 3.5 years of secured funding with the possibility of a half-year extension
- Career development, training, mentoring opportunities
- Open to all nationalities and diverse educational backgrounds

ARISE (Career Accelerator for Research Infrastructure Scientists) Call open

- **Deadline: 30 September 2023**
- Fellowship programme to train technology developers to become research infrastructure scientists with leadership prospects across sectors
- Fellows with a background in STEM

EMBL Sabbatical Visitor Fellowships Call to open: autumn 2023

- Min. 3, max. 6 months
- Visit at one of EMBL's six sites in collaboration with an EMBL team/group leader, can be co-hosted by several groups
- Up to 15,000 EUR award
- **Further fellowships available to young researchers**

Learn more: www.embl.org/training

Programmes co-funded by the Marie-Sklódowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), EC Horizon 2020 programme

EIPOD LinC: Life in Context

EIPOD-LinC is a postdoctoral fellowship programme supporting promising researchers from around the world who are passionate about interdisciplinary research

Fellows will work on a self-designed interdisciplinary research project aligned with the Molecules to Ecosystems Programme

Projects will form collaborations between EMBL labs or EMBL and **member state labs** from academic, industry, or clinical institutes

Projects must allow fellows to gain new interdisciplinary skills

Next call: second half of 2023

Learn more:

Contact: eipod@embl.de

Funding for scientific visitors and for accessing facilities

EMBL Corporate Partnership Programme Fellowship (CPP)

- Available through the **Scientific Visitor Programme**
- Collaboration hub to support the training of molecular life scientists
- **Connecting global leaders in industry** (companies with a focus on life sciences and biopharmaceutical R&D)
- Offers opportunities to liaise with EMBL's technology transfer subsidiary, **EMBLEM**

Christian Boulin Fellowships

- **Support for travel and accommodation costs** at EMBL facilities at all sites (up to 1500 EUR)
- Available for scientific visitors **from EMBL member states** for the **use of Core Facilities**
- **Applications can be submitted any time**

Funding to access EMBL Imaging Centre

ic-contact@embl.de

- **Via imaging infrastructures and access programmes:**
 - INSTRUCT ERIC
 - Euro-BiolImaging ERIC
 - European access programmes (iNEXT Discovery, ISIDORE, CanSERV)
 - Corporate Partnership Programme
 - Christian Boulin Fellowship

Thank you!

contact: maria.ananchenkova@embl.de

EMBL Core Facilities & Services

Linking science with service

Scientific Services

Data Resources

Enabling **key research on human and planetary health**: new molecular data portals on humans, pathogens, hosts

EMBL Imaging Centre

Unique worldwide, to offer member states **latest pre-commercial imaging technologies**, access to new instruments, expertise and data analysis

Structural Biology

Build on existing activities and integrate complementary structural biology services across EMBL's sites

Core Facilities

EMBL's core facilities **support and advance research** and technology development within its member states giving access to infrastructure, expertise, and quality assurance

Missions of EMBL Core Facilities and Scientific Services

- Providing high quality services to EMBL scientists, visitors and scientists from member states
- Offering access to and expertise in cutting-edge technology
- Contributing to internal and external training courses and workshops
- Contributing to technology developments in collaboration with industrial partners
- Aligning services with EMBL's scientific objectives

EMBL Scientific services

- Data resources and tools, web-based: EMBL-EBI
- Structural biology & imaging: EMBL Barcelona, Hamburg, Heidelberg & Grenoble
- Multi-omics facilities: EMBL Heidelberg & Rome
- Chemical biology services: EMBL Heidelberg
- *In vivo* gene editing services: EMBL Rome

<https://www.embl.org/services-facilities/>

EMBL-EBI data resources

EMBL Hamburg

Integrated research services in structural biology:
from diffraction patterns to structure
Project support from start to finish

Thomas Schneider
thomas.schneider@embl-hamburg.de

**Sample Preparation
and Characterization**

Beamlines

**Computational
Services**

EMBL Grenoble: HTX – the integrated facility for crystallography

- Online crystallography (protein to structure pipeline)
- Large scale fragment and ligand screening
- Membrane proteins crystallization (LCP)
- **New:** Plate-to-beam data collection (CrystalDirect at MASSIF1, cryogenic and RT)

Jose A. Marquez
marquez@embl.fr

<https://www.embl.org/services-facilities/grenoble/high-throughput-crystallisation/>

High-throughput crystallization

CrystalDirect™ automated harvesting

Automated X-ray data collection

CRIMS
Developed by EMBL
Crystallization Information Management System

Automated data processing

e.g. GlobalPhasing Pipedream

EMBL Core Facilities in Heidelberg

Genomics
Vladimir Benes

Access to and support of
CF's specific technology
& methods
Data analysis assistance
Training

Light microscopy
Rainer Pepperkok

Proteomics
Mikhail Savitski

Operated by 52 staff
Total of 1200 users/year
400 external users/year

Electron microscopy
Yannick Schwab

Protein expression
& purification
Kim Remans

Flow cytometry
Diana Ordonez

Metabolomics
Theodore Alexandrov

Chemical biology
Ulrike Uhrig

Different Core facilities - Different service models

Access-to-technology CFs

Advanced Light Microscopy
Electron Microscopy
Flow Cytometry

Service provided

Teaching of users in *instrument operation*
Consultations
Equipment maintenance and development

Users carry out their experiments

Service-based CFs

GeneCore
Proteomics
Protein expression and purification
Metabolomics
Chemical biology

Service provided

Teaching of users in *methodology*
Consultations
Equipment maintenance and development

Facility staff carries out experiments

An access model

Access-to-technology CFs

Advanced Light Microscopy
Electron Microscopy
Flow Cytometry

Access

Competitive booking by users (internal/external)
Daily usage restrictions depending on capacity
Special projects are possible

Service-based CF

Gene Core
Proteomics
Protein expression and purification

Access

'First come, first served'
Special projects are possible

Chemical biology

CBCF committee sets priorities

If interested, please contact the specific Core facility Head

Development of cross-facilities workflows: Phenomics correlation of phenotypes with their multi-omic states

Identification of phenotypes
ALMF

Isolation of phenotypic cells
FCCF

Single cell analyses
GeneCore

Christian Boulin Fellowships

- The fellowships support travel and accommodation cost of young scientists from Member & Prospect States visiting EMBL Core Facilities to benefit from access to the latest scientific techniques
- Funds provided by the Corporate Partnership Programme (CPP)
- ~15 fellowships annually, up to 1500 € each
- **www.embl.org/services-facilities/boulin-fellowships/**
- Email: **boulinfellowship@embl.de**

Mobile services (MS)

Why Mobile Services ?

Biological accessibility

A large part of the biological diversity is uncultivable

Availability

Molecular methods are often not available at field station

Comparability

Standardized processing is imperative for large scale analyses

Mobile services - Molecular biology into the field

Four complementary key technologies

Electron Microscopy prep

From volume EM of small animals to structural biology of proteins

Single cell transcriptomics

Accessing cellular heterogeneity in (non-) model organism

Feedback microscopy

Identification, imaging and labeling of organisms of interest

Image-enabled cell sorting

Accessing populations, sub-populations and phenotypes

Tara Schooner

Mobile Services

EMBL

Fondation **tara**océan

EMBR
EUROPEAN
MARINE
BIOLOGICAL
RESOURCE
CENTRE

Understand ecosystems along Europe's coastlines

120

sampling sites around

46

institutional stops in

22

countries

Thank you!

Access of EMBL services via Euro-BioImaging

EMBL's imaging services can be openly accessed via the Euro-BioImaging EMBL-Node

EMBL imaging services

EMBL advanced microscopy techniques

Funding instruments

How to access EuBio services?

- Electron Microscopy Core Facility (EMCF)
- Advanced Light Microscopy Facility (ALMF)
- Imaging Centre
- Mesoscopic Imaging Facility (MIF)

- FRAP,
- FRET,
- FCS,
- high-throughput microscopy,
- laser nanosurgery,
- CLEM,
- mesoscopy,
- super-resolution microscopy

- **ISIDORe** (projects in infectious diseases - Horizon Europe)
- **canSERV** (Cancer related projects)
- **AgroSERV** (launch Sept.2023)
- **COMULIS Mobility Grants** for Short-Term Scientific Missions
- **EMBO Short-Term Fellowships**
- The Company of Biologists' **Travelling Fellowships**

1. Select **technology** and **Node**
2. **Submit proposal**
3. **To-dos after proposal submission**

Core Facilities @ EMBL

- Current molecular biology is technology savvy
- Funding of heavy-duty instrumentation is mostly not easy for research groups of the EMBL scale
- Economy of centralization enables acquisition of state-of-the-art equipment and manageable operational cost
- Dedicated, highly qualified staff *support* scientists in their projects *facilitated* by frequent & open interactions with users, whose time is 'limited'
- “bottom-up” approach to implementation of new technology to core facilities, inter-CFs projects, synergies
- Core facilities are also regularly reviewed!
- ‘Reasonable’ prices (strictly non-profit)
- Frequently, CFs are the first contact point for the Industry

Advanced Light Microscopy CF: Pushing Limits of Visible Light

Rainer Pepperkok
pepperko@embl.de
almf@embl.de

- The first CF, inspiration for the rest; it also set the paradigm for interaction with industry, currently 30 microscope systems
- **Teaching** and **support** of users throughout the whole process of image data acquisition, analysis and documentation
- Development of streamlined application protocols, e.g. by automation, design, set-up, test and offering new equipment in collaboration with industrial partners
- siRNA HT screening libraries

<https://www.embl.org/groups/advanced-light-microscopy-core-facility/>

Electron Microscopy CF

Yannick Schwab
yannick.schwab@embl.de
emcf@embl.de

<https://www.embl.org/groups/electron-microscopy-core-facility/>

Protein Expression and Purification CF

Kim Remans

kim.remans@embl.de
pepcore@embl.de

- Production and purification of proteins from *E. coli*, insect and mammalian cells
- Collection of expression vectors and bacterial strains
- Production of enzymes for daily lab work
- Biophysical analyses (AUCFG, calorimetry)

<https://www.embl.org/groups/protein-expression-purification/>

Proteomics CF

Mikhail Savitski
mikhail.savitski@embl.de
pcf@embl.de

- Infrastructure for identification, characterization and multiplexed quantification of proteins
- Identification and quantification of post-translational modifications
- Global and targeted proteome profiling
- Steps towards reduction of required input amount thanks to implementation of beads
- Data analysis

<https://www.embl.org/groups/proteomics>

Chemical Biology CF

Ulrike Uhrig
ulrike.uhrig@embl.de

- Interfacing biology with chemistry
- Providing academic research groups access to screen small-molecule compound collections against their targets
- Identification of novel low molecular weight compounds to use as “biotools” to probe biological function
- Characterization of detected interactions
- Generating added value IP on in-house targets
- Medicinal chemistry, the compound synthesis

<https://www.embl.org/groups/chemical-biology/>

Typical Project Workflow

Flow Cytometry CF

Diana Ordonez
diana.ordonez@embl.de
fccf-team@embl.de

- Access to high-end FACS analysis
- Sorting heterogeneous populations according to many different criteria (cells, chromosomes) into homogeneous populations for experiments
- Analysis of single cell populations based on fluorescent probes and light intensities
- Imaging cell sorter

<https://www.embl.org/groups/flow-cytometry-heidelberg/>

Metabolomics CF

Theodore Alexandrov
theodore.alexandrov@embl.de
mcf@embl.de

- Global metabolite/metabolomic profiling
- Targeted metabolomic profiling
- Lipidomic analysis
- Identification of small molecules and metabolites
- LC-MS development for special applications
- Data analysis

<https://www.embl.org/groups/metabolomics/>

Genomics CF

Vladimír Beneš
benes@embl.de
genecore@embl.de

- Assisting scientists with unlocking genomes of their interest
- Complete sample processing for:
 - NGS applications for short- & long-read sequencing
 - single-cell genomic analyses (NGS, qPCR)
- Full qPCR support
- Liquid handling automation of protocols
- Assistance with data analysis
- Collection of fruitfly, nematode, mouse cDNAs

<https://www.embl.org/groups/genomics/>

Core Facilities charging mode

- Every CF is asking user fees according to the same model
- Fees cover reagents, consumables and maintenance costs
- Subsidized activity: equipment, staff and infrastructure are not included